

MapOnTap: Understanding Everyday User Context and Spatial Behaviour in Mobile Map Apps through Touchscreen Interactions

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Abstract

Research over the years has highlighted several pressing issues in the design of mobile map apps, particularly the reliance on a one-size-fits-all approach that fails to consider users' dynamic contexts and individual differences [6]. This generalised design often results in a less-than-optimal user experience, leading to frustration and increased cognitive load, which can hinder information processing and negatively affect spatial knowledge [10].

Individual differences in spatial abilities, such as spatial visualisation, sense of direction, working memory, and emotional factors like spatial anxiety, play a critical role in daily interactions with mobile maps. Indeed, emerging evidence suggests that heavy reliance on GPS-based navigation may impair these skills and hinder knowledge acquisition, indicating a correlation between GPS usage and diminished spatial capabilities [5, 3, 2]. Therefore, it is essential to account for each user's unique circumstances and cognitive resources, emphasising the need for personalised and user-centric designs. Achieving optimal mobile map design requires a deep understanding of the varied contexts in which users engage with these applications. Effective user profiling and personalisation rely on accurately capturing when, where, and how individuals use mobile maps. Despite significant progress in understanding the impact of GPS use on users' contexts and cognitive abilities, most research has relied on controlled experimental designs, whether conducted indoors or outdoors [4, 9], and self-reported data to measure GPS use [7]. This approach limits the ability to generalise findings to more complex, real-world settings. For example, self-reported GPS usage often reflects an individual's perception rather than providing an objective measurement, which can differ significantly from data collected directly from navigation-related mobile apps. This discrepancy highlights a critical research gap in understanding the connection between spatial abilities, emotional dispositions, and smartphone-based navigation in a changing context. Methods that ensure privacy while accurately capturing real-world interactions are needed to bridge this gap. One potential solution is retrieving smartphone log data, a method well-established in the human-computer interaction (HCI) field to analyse general mobile app usage patterns [8]. However, collecting ecologically valid smartphone log data specific to mobile map applications is rare and challenging, particularly in collecting data that accurately represents real-world behaviour and maintains user privacy. To our knowledge, to date, only one study in the HCI field has employed this approach by continuously collecting map-related usage data from users' mobile devices [8]. This study used a wrapper application to identify various map usage scenarios, such as map-view manipulation, searching, and place-marking. However, the research focused exclusively on Google Maps, limiting its insights to just one application.

To fully understand the diversity of mobile map apps, exploring more than just one application and considering geographic context and user spatial behaviour is necessary. Recent advances in cognitive neuroscience present promising methodologies, such as analysing touch-event sequences (taps) on smartphone screens. These methods offer unique insights into human behavioural and cognitive processes [1]. When combined with geographic context data from smartphone sensors, touch-event analysis could yield novel insights into how people use mobile map apps in real-world environments.

To this end, this PhD research proposes a novel approach, utilising a smartphone app to continuously collect time-sequenced touchscreen interactions, specifically on mobile map apps in real-life scenarios. This method is designed to overcome the limitations of traditional data collection, which often involves controlled settings and lacks privacy protection, thereby providing a fresh perspective on mobile map usage. The ultimate goal of this project is to develop a

comprehensive understanding of mobile map interactivity within real-life contexts and to integrate this knowledge into the broader framework of daily smartphone usage patterns. By combining touchscreen interaction data from mobile maps with additional geographic contextual information gathered through smartphone sensors—including GPS, accelerometers, and ambient light—this research aims to significantly enhance understanding of the complex interplay between users' physical and digital spaces. Furthermore, by incorporating individual differences, such as self-assessed spatial behaviour measures like the sense of direction or emotions like spatial anxiety, this research extends the context to include each user's unique characteristics. The final objective is to construct a predictive model for mobile map app usage based on this enriched contextual knowledge, which could lead to more effective and personalised mobile map applications.

■ **Figure 1** Screenshots of the MapOnTap app interface. The left image displays the data collection notification, informing users about the data collected, including touchscreen interactions, app usage, GPS location, time zone, and device orientation. The right image shows the list of recorded locations, each with a timestamp and the associated GPS accuracy.

Regarding the methods, this research utilised the MapOnTap app, available on Android systems, a tap-counting app developed in collaboration with QuantAction (Sàrl). The app facilitated data collection across two distinct phases. The first phase, MoT 1, occurred from February 2021 to March 2022, involving 53 participants, while the second phase, MoT 2, took place between March 2023 and June 2023, with 61 participants. Participants for both phases were recruited via the university's official email list, LinkedIn, and the research group's website. After accessing the study's website and agreeing to the consent form, individuals completed their registration. Each participant was assigned a randomised identification code via email to ensure anonymity, with email addresses managed solely by the study coordinator.

Following registration, participants installed the MapOnTap app from the Google Play Store. The app was designed to run unobtrusively in the background, recording data from when the phone was unlocked until it was locked again. The data collected included the total number of taps per session, session duration, the apps used during each session, and the categories of these apps as listed in the Google Play Store. If participants opted in, the app recorded GPS coordinates, capturing latitude, longitude, and altitude. Participants were instructed to use their smartphones as usual while the app ran in the background for at least two weeks. Importantly, participants maintained complete control over the data collection process and could stop recording, turn off GPS tracking, or uninstall the app anytime.

MoT 1 and MoT 2 adhered to ethical standards and received approval from the UZH PhF Ethics Committee under protocols Nr. 19.12.6 and Nr. 23.03.24, respectively¹. Compensation for

¹ Ethik in der Forschung³, University of Zurich, last accessed 18 March 2024,

participation differed between the two phases: MoT 1 participants were entered into a lottery for a tablet. In contrast, MoT 2 participants received a 20 Swiss franc voucher from Amazon or Digitec, a Swiss electronics retailer. The key difference between the two phases was that MoT 2 introduced a mandatory one-hour orientation session to assist with app installation and included collecting demographic data such as gender and age. In addition, MoT 2 involved distributing questionnaires to assess spatial skills, including the Santa Barbara Sense of Direction, Spatial Anxiety, and the frequency and experience of using various navigation systems like pedestrian, in-car, and paper-based maps [3, 2, 9]. MoT 2 also expanded data collection to include sensor data from accelerometers, ambient light sensors, and magnetometers. Conversely, MoT 1 was limited to collecting GPS and tap data without socio-demographic information or self-assessment questionnaires.

Preliminary findings from two exploratory studies using the tappigraphy method validated tappigraphy and its significance in grasping contextual and interactive behaviour in mobile map application design. The first study, analysing data from 38 participants, identified various tap-counting patterns across different locations for mobile maps and other app categories [12]. However, the analysis did not reveal significant differences in tap density between map apps and other app categories relative to the distance from participants' homes, suggesting the need for more detailed analysis. The second study extended these analyses by clustering mobile map app taps at different home locations, uncovering distinct interaction patterns such as 'home behaviour', characterised by high interactions near home, and 'travel behaviour' characterised by lower interactions over a broader range of distances [11]. These findings highlight the potential of tappigraphy in capturing real-world mobile app usage behaviours and demonstrate how contextual factors, such as proximity to home, influence app interaction patterns. However, both studies were limited by the absence of demographic data, such as gender, age, or detailed spatial behaviour assessments. This lack of data restricted the depth of analysis regarding individual differences in spatial behaviour and mobile map app usage. To address this latter limitation, we collected data in a second phase, including demographic information and self-assessments related to spatial anxiety, sense of direction, and navigation system usage. Preliminary results from this phase, presented as a short paper at the COSIT 2024 Conference, reveal insights into the effects of users' spatial abilities and emotional dispositions on touchscreen interactions with mobile map apps. Contrary to our hypotheses, users with a better sense of direction did not necessarily spend less time on mobile map apps, and those with higher spatial anxiety did not always spend more time on these apps. Notably, the results showed gender-specific trends: Women with higher spatial anxiety tended to switch more frequently between different app categories during phone sessions. At the same time, men with a better sense of direction spent more time using mobile map apps.

In conclusion, these findings demonstrate the potential of innovative methods like tappigraphy to capture real-world mobile app usage behaviours and emphasise the importance of integrating user-specific factors into mobile map app design. This work establishes a foundation for developing more personalised mobile map applications by understanding the diverse needs of users in real-world contexts. Additionally, it paves the way for future work on creating predictive models capable of detecting changes in a dynamic context of users and their differences, tasks and goals while employing mobile map applications.

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